

THE WORLD BANK

CDA NEWSLETTER

A PUBLICATION OF THE CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE, BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO, NIGERIA

Volume 7 No.4

OCTOBER - DECEMBER 2019

ISSN: 2350-210X

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CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, Alhaji Sabo Nanono (middle) inspecting CDA Training & Research Farm. With him are VC, Prof M.Y Bello (left) and Director, CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (right)

Minister of Agriculture Commissions CDA's Training and Research Farm

The Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, Alhaji Sabo Mohammed Nanono, on Friday, 20th December, 2019 commissioned Centre for Dryland Agriculture's training and research farm.

The farm, which is a 22-hectare modern facility, is planned for all year round agricultural production and is the biggest and first of its kind in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. The farm is fully equipped with facilities for drip and sprinkler irrigation, fertigation,

Director CDA, Prof Jibrin (middle) explaining a point to Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development and other dignitaries

in-field and controlled environment for crop production.

Alhaji Nanono said he was aware of the CDA's achievements as one of the best performing Africa centres of excellence, noting that this was possible with the support of the University Management. He called for further collaboration between BUK and his ministry to build human capacity in land and water management to help combat the challenges of climate change and its effect on overall productivity.

The farm is fully equipped with facilities for drip and sprinkler irrigation, fertigation, in-field and controlled environment for crop production

Director Laboratory Management, Dr. Ahmad Ali (left) briefing Minister of Agric about CDA laboratory equipment

CDA's ACE Impact Project Launched

ACE National Coordinator, Dr. Joshua Attah, representing the NUC Executive Secretary, Prof A.A Rasheed during the launch of CDA ACE Impact Project

The Minister of Education, Malam Adamu Adamu, has formally launched the CDA's Africa Centres of Excellence for Development (ACE Impact) on Friday, 20th December, 2019. He congratulated the Bayero University and specifically the CDA for winning the World Bank's \$5m ACE Impact grant.

The Minister of Education, who was represented by the Director Public Affairs in the National Universities Commission (NUC), Alhaji Ibrahim Usman Yakasai, said Bayero University has achieved significant milestones in addressing some of the key challenges facing sub-Saharan Africa through the Africa Centre for Excellence in Dryland Agriculture.

In his remarks, the Executive Secretary of the National Universities Commission (NUC), Professor Abubakar Adamu Rasheed, who was represented by

the ACE National Coordinator, Dr. Joshua Attah, stated that the ACE project was initiated to promote regional specialization among universities in the participating West and Central African countries and the aim was to strengthen high quality training and applied research. He said CDA was not just a BUK project but regional project helping to address common regional challenges.

The NUC Executive Secretary enumerated a number of successes recorded by the CDA to include among others enrolment of international students from 11 countries, winning additional grant of \$5m from World Bank, collaborating with many national and international organizations, generating over N150m revenue on its own and proving to be one of the top performing ACEs in Africa.

The Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin said under the ACE Impact Project, CDA would consolidate

on its previous achievements and work with relevant sectoral key players to develop and mount trainings, research and outreach programmes that will make impact on the livelihoods of the peoples of the dryland areas of West and Central Africa.

The Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, gave a brief background of the Centre which started from a humble beginning in 2012 to metamorphose into one of the competitive academic centres of excellence in the West and Central Africa (WCA) sub-region.

He said in the last five years, the Centre enrolled 315 MSc and 84 PhD students from 11 countries of the West and Central Africa sub-region and it trained more-than 2000 professionals in various skills through short-term courses.

“The short course programmes focus on professional capacity developments that impart critically needed skills in the area of food production, processing and value addition,” the Director said.

Earlier in his remarks, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello said he was highly impressed with the Minister of Agriculture's visit to launch the farm as well as his laudable support and contributions. He emphasized that the CDA would continue to address the critical challenges facing West and Central Africa and build the capacity of people through short and long term trainings to contribute to the human resource development.

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano won a World Bank Africa Centres of Excellence (ACE) Impact Grant along with 43 other centres from 12 West and Central African countries. The Centres were competitively selected under a \$300 million World Bank and French Development Agency-funded project aimed at scaling up postgraduate education and applied research.

Chairman, CDA International Scientific Advisory Board, **Professor Jimmy Adegoke**, presenting his remarks

In the last five years, the Centre enrolled 315 MSc and 84 PhD students from 11 countries of the West and Central Africa sub-region and it trained more-than 2000 professionals in various skills through short-term courses

Minister of Agric, Alhaji Sabo Nanono being flanked by BUK's Pro-Chancellor, Prof Ibrahim Gambari (right) and NUC Director of Public Affairs, Alhaji Ibrahim Yakasai

BUK Signs Agreement with PASET on PhD Programmes

Bayero University has officially signed an agreement with Partnership for Skills in Applied Science, Engineering and Technology (PASET) after being competitively selected to host PhD programmes in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change at the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA). The agreement was signed on Monday, 7th October, 2019 in Nairobi, Kenya along with other ten universities selected by PASET to host its programmes.

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello signed on behalf of Bayero University, while PASET was represented by Dr Segenet Kelemu in the presence of the Kenyan Minister of Education, Prof George AO Magoha, who was represented by the Director of University Education in the Ministry; Ambassadors, Executive Director of PASET Board, other Vice Chancellors, World Bank officials and Prof Mohamedbhai, Chairman of the PASET Advisory Group as well Deans of Graduate Schools and Directors of the Centres of Excellence from the host Universities.

Speaking after signing the agreement, Prof Bello assured PASET that BUK would be committed to the initiative and ensure that all enrolled candidates received the best form of training and are able to complete their programmes without delay. He said BUK would provide an excellent environment for scholars across Africa to come and learn on the campus without stress.

The Vice Chancellor also thanked PASET for its rigorous assessment in the selection process and assured to promote the objective of the initiative

to train 10,000 African Scientists in the next ten years.

The Kenyan Minister of Education, Prof George Magoha, who is also the Chairman of the Governing Council of PASET, said that enhancing the quality of doctoral training in our Universities required strong research base, relevant qualified staff, funding and appropriate policy to drive the science agenda.

In this regard, PASET has signed partnership agreements with seven Universities in some developed countries for students to spend short periods in their research and training facilities in the course of their doctoral studies. He argued that the knowledge generated in our Universities must result in transformative technologies, economic diversification and growth for Africa.

In her remarks, the Director General of ICIPE, managers of the Fund, Dr Segenet Kelemu, commended the eleven selected African Universities on passing the strenuous competitive selection process. She said the aim of the Fund is to train 10,000 PhDs in the five thematic areas in the host universities in the next ten years. She reassured the Universities of total support to ensure that they are able to build and sustain global best practices in research, training and capacity building through PhD, research and innovation grants.

Two other Nigerian Universities, the University of Port Harcourt and the African University of Science and Technology, Abuja together with BUK were among the ten African Universities that signed the agreement as selected Host Universities on the continent for the RSIF PhD trainings.

The Vice Chancellor of BUK was accompanied by the Dean, School of Postgraduate Studies, Professor Umaru Pate and the Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin.

Vice Chancellor, BUK, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, signing the agreement

Vice Chancellor of BUK, Prof M.Y. Bello leading the BUK Teams at ACE Bi-Annual Workshop in Dakar, Senegal

VC LEADS BUK TEAMS TO ACE BI-ANNUAL WORKSHOP IN DAKAR

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, led a team from Bayero University Kano (BUK) to the 11th bi-annual workshop of the Africa Centers of Excellence (ACE) in Dakar, Senegal. The Workshop was organized from 23rd to 28th September 2019 by the World Bank and the Association of African Universities (AAU) to review progress of the implementation of the ACE project and accelerate preparations for the kick-off of the second phase of the project tagged “ACE for Development Impact” or simply “ACE Impact” project.

The Workshop was declared open by the Senegalese Minister of Higher Education, Research and Innovation, Dr. Cheik Oumar Anne, who expressed his pride in the work that has been done by the World Bank, AAU, participating African governments and the ACE institutions in providing quality education in Africa.

Earlier, the Secretary General of the AAU, Professor Etienne Ehile, thanked His Excellency Mr.

Maki Sall, President of the Republic of Senegal and the entire Government of Senegal, for their immense efforts in supporting higher education in Senegal and Africa in general. In her speech, the Head of Education Division of the French Development Agency (AFD), Ms Veronique Sauvat, stated that AFD was attracted to the ACE Project because of the regional scope of the program and the thematic areas covered. “The project aligns to the AFD strategy”, she added.

The ACE Task Team Leader (TTL), Ms Himdat Bayusuf, made presentation on the disbursement-linked results (DLRs) achieved by the 22 ACE 1 Centers. She stated that the averaged result achieved by Centres was 83%, with the CDA topping the list with 97%.

With the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and the Africa Center of Excellence in Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP), Bayero University is one of few elite Universities with more than one ACE.

Other members of the BUK team include Professors J. M. Jibrin, S. G. Mohammed and A. Mustapha from CDA; Professor H. S. Galadanci, and Drs I. Nashabaru and B. Maiyaki from ACEPHAP; and Mr U. G. Ohikere and Mr R. H. Sagagi, who respectively served as Finance Officer and Procurement Officer for both Centres.

FG Seeks CDA's Collaboration to Boost Food Production

The Federal Government has sought collaboration with the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) of Bayero University, Kano to boost food production in the country.

The Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, Alhaji Sabo Nanono stated this during the official commissioning of CDA's Training and Research Farm and Launching of ACE Impact on 20th December, 2019.

The Minister observed that the CDA has all it takes in terms of high level manpower and state of the art facilities to partner with the federal government and other relevant institutions to address food shortage in view of the government's continued commitment to boost food production and provide job opportunities.

The Minister, who inspected the state-of-the-art agricultural analytical laboratory equipment, congratulated Bayero University and the CDA for establishing one of the best, modern and biggest training and research farms in Nigeria.

Minister of Agriculture (right) and Director of CDA (left) in a tête-à-tête

CDA Contributes to National Security - Prof. Gambari

The Pro-Chancellor and Chairman of the Bayero University Kano (BUK) Governing Council, Professor Ibrahim Gambari said the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) through its activities is contributing significantly to national security by addressing challenges of unemployment, food production, wealth creation and poverty alleviation.

Professor Gambari, who made this remark at the commissioning of CDA Training and Research Farm, emphasized that the farm couldn't have come at a better time, when the attention of the

Pro-Chancellor & Chairman of the BUK Governing Council, Professor Ibrahim Gambari presenting his address during the commissioning of CDA Farm

federal government has shifted towards boosting agricultural productivity. He noted that with sufficient food production, the challenges of national security would be significantly addressed.

Presenting his welcome address, the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, highlighted the achievements of the centre and said that the resources and facilities in the CDA could be harnessed to strongly support the federal government's efforts towards improving agricultural productivity and diversifying the economy.

APPEALS Trainees during a field tour of CDA Poultry Farm

A group photograph of CDA Team and officials of Save the Children International from Yobe State

CDA Interacts with Save the Children International to Develop Work Plan for EU Resilience Project

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) interacted with Save the Children International (SCI), a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) to develop a work plan for EU Resilient Project in Yobe State on 21st October, 2019 at the Conference Hall of CDA.

SCI is the world's leading independent organization for children that strives to give children an environment in which their human rights and needs are respected and protected so that they can realize their full potential.

The Programme Manager for EU Resilience in Yobe State, Atiku Muhammad Yola said the objective of the project was targeting resilience to provide capacity development and succour to poor communities in Yobe State. He said they came to seek the assistance of the CDA to work together as collaborators particularly in the

area of building resilience and livelihood.

Under livelihood, he explained that SCI has several agricultural approaches in which it wants the CDA to help, especially in curriculum development and guidelines for the training modules they wanted the centre to help especially in the curriculum development and guidelines for the training modules of extension agents and farmers.

For the resilience activities, "we are targeting issues of environmental impact assessment, environmental protection and management, which will all be implemented at the rural areas. We know that the CDA has the capacity and expertise to train and develop the modules as well as train the participants at the community level," he explained.

The Programme Manager

stated that at the end of the interactive session, a joint work plan will be developed so that the CDA and SCI would work together as a team to implement the project.

The Save the Children International made extensive presentations on EU Resilience Activities and Approaches towards achieving their goals in the target state.

Earlier in his opening remarks, the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, welcomed the Save the Children International (SCI) officials and assured them that the Centre would assist tremendously to develop the work plan for EU Resilience Project in Yobe State.

During the interactive session, staff of the Faculties of Agriculture, Earth and Environmental Sciences and CDA made valuable contributions towards developing viable and effective work plan for the EU Resilience Project.

CDA Team and officials of APPEALS from Kano and Kogi during the closing ceremony of first batch of training

CDA Trains First Batch of 572 Youth, Women from Kano and Kogi States on Agricultural Value Chains

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) trained the first batch of five hundred and seventy two youth and women under Agro-Processing Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood Improvement Support Project (APPEALS) on rice, fisheries and poultry value chains on Friday, 27th December, 2019. The trainees were from Kano and Kogi states.

The Agro Processing, Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood Improvement Support –**APPEALS** Project is a six-year project developed by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (**FMARD**) in collaboration with the World Bank and other stakeholders.

The Project is in line with the Agricultural Promotion Policy (**APP**) 2016-2020 of the Federal Government of Nigeria, also known as the Green Alternative, which built on the legacy of the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (**ATA**); and plans to support policy thrusts on Food Security, Local Production, Job Creation and Economic Diversification.

The CDA had earlier been contracted by Kano and Kogi APPEALS Project to train 600 and 400 beneficiaries respectively. The 572 beneficiaries trained were the first batch of the training programme for the two states.

Speaking at the closing ceremony for the first batch, the Director, Centre for Dryland Agriculture, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, who was represented by the Deputy Director, Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, enjoined the participants to maximally use what they learned by putting them into practise. He congratulated them for being selected to participate in the two-week intensive training.

The Managing Director of Kano Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (KNARDA), Ibrahim Suleiman Dan Isle congratulated the participants for earning the certificates from one of the strategic Africa centres of excellence and cautioned them to make a comprehensive business plan that would contribute meaningfully to the economic development of Kano State.

The Kano State Project Coordinator of APPEALS Project, Hassan Ibrahim, said the participants should count themselves lucky as 38, 282 people applied for the training, but only 1600 applicants from Kano were successful.

The Coordinator explained that the 1600 participants were distributed across three institutions with BUK and Kano University of Science and Technology given 600 participants each, while Audu Bako College of

Agriculture trained 400 of them. He commended the CDA for impacting positively on the lives of the trainees and assured that APPEALS would continue to partner with the Centre in future endeavours.

The trainees took time to praise the CDA for capacitating them with modern methods of agricultural value chains that will add value to their livelihood and help them to become self-reliant.

Hajiya Lubabatu Lawan, a poultry value chain trainee, thanked Almighty Allah for the knowledge acquired and assured that she would use it to train others especially women to benefit. She also thanked the trainers for teaching her new methods of poultry farming.

A fishery value chain beneficiary, Malama Hajara Hamza, had short of words to thank the APPEALS, BUK and CDA for taking her to the limelight of new knowledge of fishery farming that would go on to help her become self-reliant. She expressed the hope that it would boost the economy of the state.

On his part, Hudan Ahmad Abdullahi, who was trained on rice value chain, said he was proud of what he learned and expressed gratitude to God for being selected out of thousand applicants.

A cross section of trainees from Kogi State listening to a presentation from Professor Aminu Sulaiman

Professor Amina Mustapha, the Coordinator of APPEALS Training, explaining a point to the participants during a field tour to Rice Processing Mill

Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (right) briefing Minister of Agriculture, BUK Pro-Chancellor and other dignitaries about the CDA modern laboratory equipment

Minister of Agriculture Inspects State-of-the-Art CDA Laboratories Equipment

The Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, Alhaji Sabo Mohammed Nanono, inspected state-of-the-art laboratories equipment of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) on 20th December, 2020. It was part of the tour of CDA facilities during the commissioning of CDA Training and Research Farm.

The Minister congratulated Bayero University and the CDA for acquiring such facilities of international standards. He said the Federal Government would continue to partner with the Centre.

Some of the equipment inspected include:

1) Ion Chromatograph (Metrohm)

The Metrohm Compact IC Flex is a versatile ion chromatograph engineered with a focus on the analysis of anions, cations and carbohydrates in almost any kind of sample. The equipment is compact and modular and an excellent choice for clearly defined analytical requirements. Metrohm IC uses any kind of suppression, equipped with UV/VIS, conductivity, or amperometric detectors, inline ultra-filtration, inline dilution, inline dialysis that enables high-through-put analysis and user friendly software.

2) 4200 Agilent MP AES

The 4200 MP AES is an excellent choice for heavy metal analysis capable of analysing up to 40 elements in the periodic table in part-per billion. Its magnetically excited microwave plasma source provides superior detection limits to flame AA. In addition to eliminating flammable and oxidizing gases, the 4200 MP-AES eliminates the need to plumb multiple gases into the laboratory, or manually transport and handle gas cylinders as a nitrogen generator is in place to trap nitrogen from the air.

3) CHNSO Analyzer

The 2400 Series II CHNS/O Elemental Analyzer is one of the leading organic elemental analyzers in use today. It is ideal for the rapid determination of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulfur, and oxygen content in organic and other types of materials.

4) Gradient Thermal Cycler

The GTC96S Gradient Thermal Cycler is ideal for both thermal cycling and protocol optimization, which can be programmed to operate with uniform temperature across the block or with a horizontal gradient for rapid amplification of DNA.

5) X-Ray Fluorescence

The S2 RANGER is versatile equipment capable of analysing solids, powders or liquids for element composition from ppm-levels to 100% by using the highest power in direct excitation geometry. The CDA XRF is powerful and environmentally friendly equipment that is an alternative to AAS and ICP.

6) NIRS

The NIRS DS2500 Analyzer is a robust equipment for quantitative and qualitative analyses of solids and liquids over a full spectral range from 400 to 2500 nm and delivers accurate, reproducible results in under one minute. Its versatility makes it suitable for analysis without sample preparation.

7) Microplate Reader MultiSkán Sky

The Multiskan Sky Microplate Spectrophotometer is a UV/Vis microplate spectrophotometer capable of analysing 96 to 384 samples in just a minute. It is ideal for photometric measurements of mycotoxins, nutraceutical and other antioxidant assays, DNA and RNA, as well as protein analysis. It is suitable for a variety of endpoint, kinetic and spectral assays.

Food Analysis Equipment. These include:

8) Combustion Calorimeter

Determination of calorific value (energy) of combustible substances e.g. feed (animal & human), hydrocarbon oils etc.

9) Fibertec 8000 (Auto Fibre Analysis System)

Determination of fiber content and fiber fractions in plant tissues.

10) Kjeltec 8400 (Automatic Distillation/Titration)

Determination of nitrogen/protein content in feed (animal/human).

11) Sortec 8000 (Extraction Unit)

Determination of fat content in substances e.g. animal & human feed.

12) Hydrotec 8000

CDA to Establish Regional Innovation, Training and Entrepreneurship Accelerator

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) plans to establish a Regional Innovation, Training and Entrepreneurship Accelerator (RITEA).

This was disclosed by the Director, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin recently, who said the RITEA would provide an avenue for youth to be trained in modern intensive agriculture (both in-field and in protected environments) and in bio-resource entrepreneurship.

He said the aspect of bio-resource entrepreneurship would entail interdisciplinary approach to value addition from agricultural products and wastes.

According to him, this is towards emergence of small and medium scale enterprises (SME) that will alleviate poverty and improve the general well-being of the inhabitants of the West and Central Africa (WCA).

“The Centre will establish a

From Left: CDA Deputy Director, Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, Dean Faculty of Agriculture, Professor Bakori and Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin

dedicated training workshop/unit equipped with SME machineries coupled with development of technologies targeted at producing high value import substitution products from biomass. The

existing laboratories in the Centre would be used to support the emerging SMEs with quality control analysis and certification of their finished products, said the Director.

CDA Develops Mobile App for Fertilizer Recommendation

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has developed a mobile application based on android for fertilizer recommendation called Right Fertilizer Recommendation Tool. The application will assist farmers to apply the right fertilizer for maize production based on its recommendation and avoid inappropriate waste of resources. The application was developed under Taking Maize Agronomy to Scale in Africa (TAMASA) project.

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has partnered with the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Centre for Maize and Wheat Improvement

(CIMMYT), and International Plant Nutrition Institute (IPNI) in the TAMASA project.

The main target of the project was to close the attainable-yield gap of maize using innovative approaches that use modern large data and analytics to map maize areas, soil constraints and attainable yields at different scales. The project also aimed to identify and co-develop systems and applications that transform this data and information to useable products that support production at farmer level.

The CDA interacted with the agricultural extension agents from

Kano Agricultural Development Authority (KNARDA), Kaduna Agricultural Development Project (KADP), KATARDA of Katsina State, DAREO, NAERLS, Zaria and Sasakawa Global 2000 on the way and means to enhance the application and give it a facelift on Monday, 30th and Tuesday, 31st December, 2019.

The Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, while briefing the extension agents during the interaction on Tuesday, 31st December, 2019 expressed happiness over their contribution to enhance the application.

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